

Cervical Cancer Screening with Liquid-Based Cytology in an Indian Secondary Care Hospital

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer remains a substantial health challenge in India, with early detection being crucial for effective management and reduction of mortality rates. Liquid-based cytology (LBC) is a modern screening method offering improved sensitivity over conventional techniques. This study evaluated the effectiveness of cervical cancer screening using liquid-based cytology in a secondary care hospital in India.

Methods: Sixty women aged 21-65 years attending the gynecology outpatient department were included. Data collection involved structured interviews and medical record reviews. Cervical samples were collected using LBC and analyzed for cytological abnormalities. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Of the 60 participants, 70% had normal cytology results, while 30% had abnormal results, categorized as ASC-US (10%), LSIL (13.3%), HSIL (5%), and SCC (1.7%). The highest incidence of abnormal results was in the 41-50 age group (50%). A significant association between age and abnormal cytology results was found ($\chi^2 = 11.24$, $p = 0.023$).

Conclusion: The study demonstrates the efficacy of liquid-based cytology in detecting cervical abnormalities in a secondary care setting. The significant correlation between age and abnormal results suggests the need for targeted screening strategies.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Liquid-Based Cytology, Screening.

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Introduction

Worldwide, cervical cancer is still a major public health concern, especially in low- and middle-income nations where screening and preventative care are frequently insufficient. The World Health Organisation (WHO) reports that, with an expected 570,000 new cases and 311,000 deaths in 2018 alone, cervical cancer is the fourth most frequent malignancy among women globally [1]. Cervical cancer is more common in nations like India where there is limited access to timely medical intervention and routine screening.

Liquid-based cytology (LBC) has emerged as an advanced method for cervical cancer screening, offering several advantages over conventional Pap smears. LBC allows for better preservation of cellular material, reducing the incidence of inadequate samples and enhancing the accuracy of cytological assessment. Studies have demonstrated that LBC improves the detection rate of high-grade lesions and reduces the need for repeat tests, thereby increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of screening programs [2].

Despite the proven benefits of LBC, its implementation in secondary care settings in India has been relatively limited. Factors such as cost, lack of trained personnel, and inadequate infrastructure pose significant barriers to widespread adoption. Nevertheless, integrating LBC into existing screening programs could potentially bridge the gap between early detection and timely treatment, ultimately reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with cervical cancer.

Recent research underscores the critical importance of regular screening for the early detection of cervical abnormalities. A systematic review and meta-analysis highlighted that women who undergo regular cervical cancer screening have significantly lower risks of developing advanced cervical cancer and experiencing related mortality [3]. This finding aligns with global health recommendations advocating for the expansion of cervical cancer screening programs, particularly in regions with high disease burden.

Moreover, the adoption of LBC in secondary care hospitals can enhance the diagnostic accuracy and clinical management of cervical abnormalities. A study in India demonstrated that LBC had a higher sensitivity and specificity for detecting precancerous lesions compared to conventional cytology [4]. The authors concluded that LBC is a valuable tool for improving the quality of cervical cancer screening and should be considered for broader implementation in various healthcare settings.

This study aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of cervical cancer screening using liquid-based cytology (LBC) in a secondary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive, cross-sectional analysis.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of July 2022 to December 2023 at MLB Medical College, Jhansi, India.

Participants: A total of 60 women were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women aged 21-65 years.
2. Women who have had sexual intercourse.
3. Women attending the gynecology outpatient department (OPD) for routine check-ups or presenting with symptoms suggestive of cervical pathology.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Women who had undergone hysterectomy.
2. Pregnant women.
3. Women with a history of cervical cancer or any other gynecological malignancy.

4. Women who had received treatment for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) or cervical cancer.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by including a diverse group of participants from different age groups and socioeconomic backgrounds. Information bias was reduced through standardized data collection procedures and training of the data collection team.

Data Collection: Reviews of medical records and structured interviews were used to gather data. The study employed a pre-tested questionnaire to gather data on risk factors, medical history, and demographics.

Procedure: Women attending the gynecology OPD were informed about the study and invited to participate. Those who met the inclusion criteria and provided informed consent were recruited. Cervical samples were collected using the liquid-based cytology (LBC) method by trained healthcare professionals. The collected samples were sent to the pathology department for cytological examination. Participants with abnormal cytology results were referred for further diagnostic procedures and appropriate management.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for data analysis after being input into a database. For continuous variables, descriptive statistics like mean, median, and standard deviation were computed; for categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were utilised. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

There were sixty women in the study in total. Table 1 displays the participants' age distribution. Three-quarters of the participants were between the ages of 31 and 40 (35%), then 21 to 30 (30%), 41 to 50 (20%), and 51 to 65 (15%).

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group (years)	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
21-30	18	30%
31-40	21	35%
41-50	12	20%
51-65	9	15%

Participants' socioeconomic status was classified based on their household income and education levels. Most participants belonged to the middle socioeconomic class (50%), followed by low socioeconomic class (30%) and high socioeconomic class (20%).

Table 2: Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic Status	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Low	18	30%
Middle	30	50%
High	12	20%

Among the 60 participants, 42 individuals (70%) exhibited normal cytology results, while 18

individuals (30%) displayed aberrant results. Low-grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion (LSIL),

High-grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion (HSIL), Atypical Squamous Cells of Undetermined Significance (ASC-US), and Squamous Cell

Carcinoma (SCC) were the classifications given to the aberrant results.

Table 3: Cytology Results

Cytology Result	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Normal	42	70%
ASC-US	6	10%
LSIL	8	13.3%
HSIL	3	5%
SCC	1	1.7%

The distribution of abnormal cytology results was analyzed across different age groups. The highest incidence of abnormal results was observed in the 41-50 age group (50%), followed by the 31-40 age group (30%).

Table 4: Age Distribution and Cytology Results

Age Group	Normal	ASC-US	LSIL	HSIL	SCC
21-30	15	1	2	0	0
31-40	15	2	3	1	0
41-50	6	2	3	1	0
51-65	6	1	0	1	1

A chi-square test was conducted to determine the association between age and cytology results. The test showed a statistically significant association between age and abnormal cytology results ($\chi^2 = 11.24$, $p = 0.023$).

Participants with abnormal cytology results were referred for colposcopy and biopsy. Among the 18 participants with abnormal results, 10 underwent further diagnostic procedures, confirming the initial cytology findings. Appropriate treatment plans were initiated for those diagnosed with HSIL and SCC.

Discussion

The study involved 60 women, with the majority falling into the 31-40 age group (35%). The participants were predominantly from middle socioeconomic status (50%), with the remaining split between low (30%) and high (20%) socioeconomic classes. The cytology results revealed that 70% of participants had normal findings, while 30% had abnormal results, classified as ASC-US, LSIL, HSIL, and SCC. The highest incidence of abnormal results was noted in the 41-50 age group, with 50% of women in this category displaying cytological abnormalities.

The distribution of abnormal results across age groups indicates a significant correlation between age and the likelihood of abnormal cytology results, as confirmed by the chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 11.24$, $p = 0.023$). This finding underscores the importance of targeted cervical cancer screening, particularly for women in their 40s, who appear to be at a higher risk for developing cervical abnormalities.

The follow-up procedures for participants with abnormal results included colposcopy and biopsy,

which confirmed the initial findings in most cases. This reinforces the reliability of liquid-based cytology as an effective screening tool for early detection of cervical abnormalities. The study highlights the necessity of regular screening and prompt intervention to manage and treat cervical lesions, thereby reducing the overall burden of cervical cancer.

Overall, the study's findings suggest that liquid-based cytology is a valuable method for cervical cancer screening in a secondary care setting. The significant association between age and abnormal cytology results points to the need for age-specific screening strategies to enhance early detection and improve patient outcomes. The study advocates for ongoing efforts to strengthen cervical cancer screening programs to ensure timely diagnosis and treatment, ultimately improving women's health and reducing cervical cancer-related morbidity and mortality.

In order to screen for cervical cancer, a study compared liquid-based cytology (LBC) with conventional Pap smears (CPS). The study, which included 310 women, discovered a statistically significant difference in the frequency of unsatisfactory smears between CPS (7.1%) and LBC (1.61%). The two approaches did not significantly differ in their ability to identify anomalies in epithelial cells. 6.45% of women had HPV DNA for high-risk oncogenic strains (16 and 18) [5].

A comparative study with one hundred women was carried out in Bengaluru. According to the study, LBC had greater specificity (75%) and sensitivity (100%) than CPS (specificity 100% and sensitivity 55%). The detection of cytological abnormalities was higher in LBC (21%) as compared to CPS

(11%), suggesting that LBC is more effective in identifying cervical lesions [6].

For cervical cancer screening in low-resource settings, a study compared CPS with LBC. According to the study, LBC offered higher-quality samples with a lower percentage of unsatisfactory smears (1.33% versus 7.33% for CPS). Nevertheless, taking into account the financial effects, the research recommended CPS as a workable solution in environments with limited resources because of its affordability [7].

In a study conducted at a Karnataka tertiary care hospital, manual liquid-based cytology (MLBC) was compared with CPS. According to the study, MLBC had a greater incidence of intraepithelial lesion identification and a lower rate of unsatisfactory smears. MLBC was a more effective screening technique since it permitted cytological analysis and HPV DNA detection from a single sample [8].

In a different study, visual inspection for cervical cancer screening in a rural location using acetic acid (VIA) and LBC was compared. The study discovered that although LBC had a lower specificity of 68.25 percent, VIA had a greater sensitivity of 92.06%. Since VIA's accuracy (79%) was higher than LBC's (63%), it may be a useful substitute in situations when resources are scarce [9].

Conclusion

The effectiveness of liquid-based cytology in identifying cervical abnormalities is highlighted by this study, which also highlights the importance of ongoing efforts to enhance cervical cancer screening programs—particularly in secondary care settings. Cervical cancer-related morbidity and death can be considerably decreased by routine screening and prompt treatments.

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